

Automatic optimization and delineation of nested slope units with r.slopeunits v2.0

Massimiliano Alvioli, Ivan Marchesini

Istituto di Ricerca per la Protezione Idrogeologica, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche,
Via Madonna Alta 126, I-06128, Perugia, Italy

{massimiliano.alvioli, ivan.marchesini}@irpi.cnr.it

¹
Abstract— Slope unit delineation falls under the wider domain of geomorphological surface classification, with a few peculiarities. Surface classification is mostly achievable with variations of segmentation methods, requiring data of different nature, while (automatic) slope unit delineation only depend on the information in a digital elevation model. In particular, slope units strongly relate to the stream network in an area, which requires an extra bit of knowledge with respect to simple segmentation of the surface into areas with similar local properties. A slope unit encompasses a region of the surface of size typically ranging from a fraction to a few square kilometers, and is recognizable in the field as a hillslope. For automatic slope unit delineation, we rely on specialized software. This work introduces an updated version of the r.slopeunits software. The previous version of r.slopeunits, a GRASS GIS module published in 2016, represented a common choice for slope unit delineation in the literature. The new software introduces new features, especially the optimization of input parameters and multi-layer delineation capabilities. We briefly describe the new software, and describe preliminary results for a multi-layer slope unit map of Italy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Slope units (SUs) are an alternative to grid cells, for selected applications. Slope units and grid cells are fundamentally different mapping units, as SUs have a strong relationship with topography, absent in the square grid representation. Drainage and divide lines define SU boundaries, so that they have meaningful hydrological properties and fulfil well-defined geomorphological constraints. That gives advantages for the description of slope-related phenomena, such as landslides, using SU-aggregated quantities.

Examples of specific advantages given by SUs are the possibility of using heterogeneous data for landslide susceptibility mapping, including point or polygonal landslide inventories, and considering data-scarce areas for landslide susceptibility with statistical methods [1]. Slope unit polygons, in this case, represent geographical domains to aggregate surface descriptors

representing the predictors for landslide presence. Reducing the dimensionality of the problem from billions, independently described grid cells, to a few hundred thousands, homogeneous slope units, also renders manageable the study of very large areas in a consistent way.

Examples of different applications involve the use of SUs in conjunction with models of different nature, for example physically based methods [2-4]. In the latter case, SUs may still act as a-posterior aggregation units of model results originally obtained on grid cells [3], in difference with the use of SUs within statistical or machine learning models. Slope units may also serve as local reference boundaries for expert landslide mapping [5], or in combination with remote sensing data [6].

The continued interest in using SUs for landslide studies is supported by the recent introduction of various pieces of software designed for their automatic delineation, either using aspect homogeneity measures [7], stream order classification [8], clustering algorithms [9], or terrain topology considerations [10]. Typically, a software can produce SU maps independently of landslide susceptibility (LS) models. Examples are the SU maps of Italy [11] and of a large portion of the Himalayas [12]. The SU map of Italy was useful in a national zonation of LS for different landslide types [13]. A select subset of the map constitutes a benchmark dataset, established with the consensus of authors from several different institutions, for comparing different LS methods and developing a workflow as standardized as possible [14].

Here, we describe an update of the r.slopeunits software, designed to delineate slope units uniquely information from a digital elevation model (DEM). The original implementation, v1.0 [7], produced SU maps in a parametric way, using an adaptive algorithm to obtain half-basins of different granularity in different regions of the study area. The need to choose optimal values of input parameters hindered applicability of the software for some users. Version 2.0 includes a built-in optimization function that returns values of optimal input parameters, based on an aspect

segmentation function. As in the original implementation, SU delineation and optimization only depend on the input DEM, and requires no additional data.

The second novelty of `r.slopeunits v2.0` is the possibility of producing several maps of nested SUs. We refer to each map as an individual layer, with the number (size) of SU polygons decreasing (increasing) with increasing layer, with the base layer represented by the map produced by the built-in optimization procedure. This feature entails producing coarser SU layers with increasing values of the `cvmin` input parameter, which controls the homogeneity of aspect within each SU. Larger `cvmin` values produce larger SUs, on average. We suggest such multi-layer, hierarchical SU map as an additional tool for a multi-scale description of landslide susceptibility in large areas.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The `r.slopeunits` software v2.0 is available as a regular add-on in GRASS GIS [11] (use the tool `g.extension` to install the module from a web repository). The new implementation consists of a toolset with five sub-modules:

1. `r.slopeunits.create`, the main tool for slope unit delineation, corresponding to v1.0 of the software, as in Ref. [7].
2. `r.slopeunits.clean`, providing several options to clean small areas resulting from `r.slopeunits.create`; also included in v1.0.
3. `r.slopeunits.optimize`, which selects optimal values for input parameters of `r.slopeunits.create`, for a given area and DEM. It represents the first major novelty of v2.0 of the software.
4. `r.slopeunits.metrics`, mostly used for the optimization procedure, called by `r.slopeunits.optimize`, used in Ref. [11] but never published before.
5. `r.slopeunits.nested`, which delineates several nested layers of slopeunits. It represents the second major novelty of v2.0 of the software.

The tools no. 1-4 were ported to GRASS GIS modules, in Python language, from hybrid Python code and bash scripts, with support from URGERE project of CNR IRPI (see Section V), while porting of tool no. 5 is underway, with support from the HySTC project of CNR IRPI (see Section V).

We applied the new software, in particular tool no. 5, to the European EU-DEM at 25 m spatial resolution in Italy, as in the previous single-layered version of the SU map of Ref. [11].

The software `r.slopeunits.create` identifies slope units as half-basins with a minimum aspect homogeneity *or/and* a minimum surface area thresholds set by the user. It works iteratively: it decreases the value of an initial (user-supplied) upslope contributing area threshold at each iteration, and stops the iterations at different stages depending on the local surface. The number of iterations is not predetermined, but it is adaptive, depending on local aspect homogeneity and on the minimum surface area required by the user. In the process, the software does

not explicitly keep track of the basin/stream order hierarchy, and it only collects half-basins fulfilling the homogeneity and minimum area criteria requested by the user, by means of two input parameters `cvmin` and `areamin`.

The tool `r.slopeunits.nested` helps delineating different SU layers by running `r.slopeunits.create`, in the same area, with increasing values of the `cvmin` input parameter. In fact, the numerical values of the input parameters of the software, mainly by the `areamin` and `cvmin` parameters, control the size and shape of the output layers. Different combinations of the two parameters result in an output with a different number of slope units, with deterministic but not easily predictable shape and size. Increasing the value of `cvmin` results in SU polygons with a decreasing degree of aspect homogeneity, which corresponds to SUs of increasing size. A larger value of the `cvmin` parameter selects half-basins as slope units later in the iterative procedure than a lower value of the parameter would do. The benefit of `r.slopeunits.nested` is to produce different slope unit layers with nested edges, which is impossible to achieve with any parameter combination of the previous version of the software.

The optimized SU map of Italy introduced in Ref. [11] resulted partly from application of the algorithm implemented in `r.slopeunits.optimize`, and partly with a simple parameter scan. Use of the two options was peculiar of the method described in the quoted reference. Evaluation of the aspect segmentation metric (objective function) implemented in `r.slopeunits.metrics`, for different combination of parameters, allows selection of the optimal parameters as those corresponding to the maximum of the objective function. The process runs in parallel in each of the 439 watersheds defined for Italy in Ref. [11]. Here, the software runs separately in the same set of watersheds, keeping all input parameters fixed but `cvmin`, thus generating higher-order SU layers. Each additional SU layer was obtained selecting five different values of `cvmin`=0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7. Instead, the optimized values for `areamin` were the same obtained in Ref. [11], for each watershed. The final five new national SU maps result from merging the individual results, in each watershed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We show preliminary results for several layers of nested slope units, obtained as a multi-scale extension of the national SU map described in Ref. [11] and published at the main slope unit-project webpage, <https://geomorphology.irpi.cnr.it/tools/slope-units>.

The new layers are such that SU polygons in each lower-order layer exactly nest inside the polygons of the higher-order layer, hierarchically from layer 0 to layer 5. Layer 0 correspond to the existing, optimized result of Ref. [11]. Layers 1-5 contain a decreasing number of SU polygons, as specified in Table I. The Table also shows that minimum area of polygons remains practically the same across all the layers, while the maximum area increases significantly, with the largest percent difference between layer 0 and layer 1. As shown in Ref. [11], the size distribution of

Figure 1. Three of the six nested slope unit layers obtained in this work. (a) General setting; (b) layer 0, as in Ref. [11]; (c) layer 3 superimposed to layer 0; (d) layer 5 superimposed to layers 0 and 3. See Table I for numerical figures of the different layers.

optimized SUs in an area is skewed towards small areas, with a long tail towards large areas, and with several outliers. The last column in Table I is intended to check whether this feature remains in higher-order layer. One can appreciate that the percent of polygons with sizes larger than the average size increases monotonically from 30 % to 37 %, denoting distributions less and less skewed. One can understand this feature noting that optimized SUs (layer 0) provide a better segmentation of the topography in terms of homogenous areas. Deviating from the optimal SU set, we necessarily start merging the smaller polygons, dense in highly dissected regions, mostly leaving untouched the larger ones, located in regions with a smoother surface.

Figure 1 shows details, in Central Italy, of a subset of the new layers. We only show details of layers 0, 3 and 5, for illustration. Showing the full six layers would be very difficult in a short contribution, and we encourage interested readers to download the

vector layers at the main SU project page, to appreciate fully the nested feature of the polygons at the different scales.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We introduced version 2.0 of the software *r.slopeunits*, whose previous version represented a common choice for slope unit delineation in the recent literature. We expect that the new features of the software, especially the optimization and multi-layer delineation capabilities, will make the software even more useful and user-friendly for a wider user base.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Implementation of modules no. 1-4 of the software supported by MUR PRIN Project “URGERS: URban Geodiversity for a Resilient Environment” 2022M7EP3M_PE10_PRIN2022 - PNRR M4.C2.1.1 - Funded by the European Union – Next

Table I. Numerical figures representing the number and size distributions of the slope unit polygons in the six different nested SU layers described in this work. Layers 0, 3 and 5 are shown Figure 1.

Layer no.	Input <i>cvmin</i> value	Minimum area [km ²]	Average area [km ²]	Maximum area [km ²]	Number of polygons	% units with area > average
0	<i>Optimized (Ref. [11])</i>	0.092	0.69	15.51	325,578	29.9
1	0.3	0.096	1.02	147.73	220,308	31.2
2	0.4	0.096	1.32	267.46	170,240	34.3
3	0.5	0.096	1.55	277.20	144,430	36.5
4	0.6	0.096	1.67	277.20	133,928	37.1
5	0.7	0.096	1.72	287.81	129,961	37.3

Generation EU - CUP: B53D23007260006. Development and implementation of module no. 5 of the software supported by project HySTC/RETURN “Hydrology and Stability of slopes along Transport Corridors” CODSOG_001744 - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU - CUP C99J24000390008.

The Mundialis team, based in Germany, performed porting of all modules from the original Python/bash scripts developed by IRPI CNR to modern code standards, and implemented the code as an official GRASS GIS add-on.

REFERENCES

- Jacobs, L., M. Kervyn, P. Reichenbach, M. Rossi, I. Marchesini, M. Alvioli, O. Dewitte (2020). Regional susceptibility assessments with heterogeneous landslide information: Slope unit- vs. pixel-based approach. *Geomorphology*, 356, 107084. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2020.107084>
- Domènech, G., M. Alvioli, J. Corominas (2020). Preparing first-time slope failures hazard maps: from pixel-based to slope unit-based. *Landslides*, 17, 249–265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-019-01279-4>
- Alvioli, M., G. Falcone, A. Mendicelli, F. Mori, F. Fiorucci, F. Ardizzone, M. Moscatelli (2023). Seismically induced rockfall hazard from a physically based model and ground motion scenarios in Italy. *Geomorphology* 429, 108652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2023.108652>
- Lopez-Vinielles, J., J.A. Fernández-Merodo, P. Ezquerro, J.C. García-Davalillo, R. Sarro, C. Reyes-Carmona, A. Barra, J.A. Navarro, V. Krishnakumar, M. Alvioli, G. Herrera (2021). Combining Satellite InSAR, Slope Units and Finite Element Modeling for Stability Analysis in Mining Waste Disposal Areas. *Remote Sensing*, 13, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13102008>
- Alvioli, M., M. Santangelo, F. Fiorucci, M. Cardinali, I. Marchesini, P. Reichenbach, M. Rossi, F. Guzzetti, S. Peruccacci (2021). Rockfall susceptibility and network-ranked susceptibility along the Italian railway. *Engineering Geology*, 293, 106301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2021.106301>
- Alvioli, M., A.C. Mondini, F. Fiorucci, M. Cardinali, I. Marchesini (2018). Topography-driven satellite imagery analysis for landslide mapping. *Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk*, 9, 544-567. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19475705.2018.1458050>
- Alvioli, M., I. Marchesini, P. Reichenbach, M. Rossi, F. Ardizzone, F. Fiorucci, F. Guzzetti (2016). Automatic delineation of geomorphological slope units with r.slopeunits v1.0 and their optimization for landslide susceptibility modeling. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9, 3975–3991. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-3975-2016>
- Woodard, J.B., B.B. Mirus, N.J. Wood, K.E. Allstadt, B.A. Leshchinsky, M.M. Crawford (2024). Slope Unit Maker (SUMak): an efficient and parameter-free algorithm for delineating slope units to improve landslide modeling. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 24(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-24-1-2024>
- Li, Y., B. Fu, Z. Han, Z. Fang, N. Chen, G. Hu, W. Wang, G. Chen (2024). PSO-SLIC algorithm: A novel automated method for the generation of high-homogeneity slope units using DEM data. *Geomorphology*, 463, 109367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2024.109367>
- Zhang, L., D. Ming, Y. Li, J. Cai, Z. Zhang (2024). A new slope unit extraction method based on terrain topology searching and vector similarity constraint for landslide analysis. *Catena*, 246, 108355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2024.108355>
- Alvioli, M., F. Guzzetti, I. Marchesini (2020). Parameter-free delineation of slope units and terrain subdivision of Italy. *Geomorphology*, 358, 107124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2020.107124>
- Alvioli, M., Marchesini, I., B. Pokharel, K. Gnyawali, S. Lim (2024). Geomorphological slope units of the Himalayas. *Journal of Maps*, 18, 300-313. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17445647.2022.2052768>
- Loche, M., M. Alvioli, I. Marchesini, H. Bakka, L. Lombardo (2022). Landslide susceptibility maps of Italy: Lesson learnt from dealing with multiple landslide types and the uneven spatial distribution of the national inventory. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 232, 104125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2022.104125>
- Alvioli, M., M. Loche, L. Jacobs, C.H. Grohmann, M.T. Abraham, K. Gupta, N. Satyam, G. Scaringi, T. Bornaetxea, M. Rossi, I. Marchesini, L. Lombardo, M. Moreno, S. Steger, C.A.S. Camera, G. Bajni, G. Samodra, E.E. Wahyudi, N. Susyanto, M. Sinčić, S. Bernat Gazibara, F. Sirbu, J. Torizin, N. Schüßler, B.B. Mirus, J.B. Woodard, H. Aguilera, J. Rivera-Rivera (2024). A benchmark dataset and workflow for landslide susceptibility zonation. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 258, 104927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2024.104927>
- Neteler, M., H. Mitasova (2012). GRASS GIS: A multi-purpose open source GIS. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 31, 124-130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2011.11.014>